

Recommended citation: Bombaerts, G., Martin, D. A., Junaid, S., & Tormey, R. (2020). Coaching Engineering Ethics Education Research. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1410-1410). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14654386](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654386).

COACHING ENGINEERING ETHICS EDUCATION RESEARCH

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Engineering ethics education still faces many challenges, such as specification of what it really wants to address, how to truly engage and motivate engineering students for ethics education with activating methods or how to assess important ethical goals such as being a critical citizen or fostering moral awareness. There is a need for more and more evidence-informed Engineering Ethics Education Research to support answering these challenges.

The aim of the workshop is to address this need. As it is organized by members of the SIG Ethics, it will be one step in coaching participants to elucidate together what good research in engineering ethics education entails and to enable the SEFI community to pursue research in this area.

The online workshop will have the following structure: (1) Intro of the topic. (2) Collection and prioritization of important challenges in engineering ethics education. (3) Participants will be divided in small groups working on a topic of interest in online breakout rooms. (4) An experienced reviewer/editor gives some core recommendations on conducting research in engineering ethics education (5) Small groups come up with a first research proposal: problem description, theories to be used, research question, limitation of scope and research method. (6) The different groups present their proposals and get feedback from other groups.

The SIG Ethics will organize an event taking place between the yearly SEFI conferences of 2020 – 21 in order to continue to work on these paper proposals. As such, the workshop is a first step in an output oriented process of coaching Engineering Ethics Education Research.

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